

Navigating the data continuum

From closed to open in qualitative research?

Linde Tuybens

22 September 2025

Research Data Management (RDM) Team

- Part of the **Research Affairs Office at RIVA – Research Innovation & Valorisation Antwerp**
- Offer advice on all things related research data management, including data management plans, Nagoya, and Open Science and FAIR Data
- rdm-support@uantwerpen.be

- **Siham Benramdane** (Life Sciences & Medicine)
- **Robin Björklund** (Natural Sciences & Engineering)
- **Linde Tuybens** (Social Sciences & Humanities)
- **Dunya Nasser** (File manager)

Open Science & Open Data

- **“Open scholarship”, “Open research”**
- **Often equated with the practice of (raw) data sharing**
 - But complex landscape of different practices
 - Open data = most controversial area
- **Purpose of open data: reproducibility → transparency & usability**
- **Need for flexibility (in policies & OS practices)**
- **Broaden focus**
 - Shared data
 - Shared materials
 - Other shared outputs
 - Context documentation

Flavors of data

*“Research data are all **digital or physical data** - regardless of the manner in which these data are collected or stored - used or analyzed to **support research findings**, validate research results or underlie a scientific reasoning, discussion or calculation in the study.*

*Research data cover the entire spectrum of **raw data to processed and analyzed data** included or discussed in a publication. These data can be **reused data, derived or composite data**, as well as **self-generated data and data provided by third parties.**“*

RDM Policy of University Antwerp

No data?

What are Data?

Research data are all digital or physical objects, regardless of how they are collected or stored, that are used or analysed to support research findings and validate research results, or are underlying a reasoning, discussion, or calculation in the research.

What is Research Data Management?

Research Data Management (RDM) encompasses all practices and actions performed to ensure that research data are properly and securely collected, organised, described, preserved, and shared.

Why should you care? What is in it for you?

By applying good RDM practices, you can:

- Avoid data loss
- Avoid accusation of fraud in research
- Increase the reusability of your data
- Increase the reproducibility of your research
- Improve integrity and quality of your data and research
- Comply with legislative/funder/publisher requirements

Research Methods

(Systematic)
Literature Review

Web-based Review

Literary Analysis

Audiovisual
Media Review

Visual Analysis
& Art Review

Interviews &
Focus Groups

Archival Research

(Participant/Natural)
Observation

Ethnography /
(Ethno)Archeology

Meta-analysis

Theoretical /
Computational /
Simulation Research

Examples: (Re)Used Data

Published work of other scholars (articles, book chapters, conference papers, reports, grey literature, etc.), existing databases

Websites, web articles, blog posts, social media, news (online), other digital content

Novels, theatre plays, poetry, translations, (auto)biographies, letters, diaries

Films, audio/video clips, TV shows, advertisements, podcasts, (radio) broadcasts, production notes, promotional material

Music (scores), sculptures, paintings, stage performances, ceramics, comics, graffiti, memes, exhibition catalogues

Guidelines, interview protocols, participant profiles, visual aids

Manuscripts, photographs, maps, audiovisual material, governmental/organisational records, personal papers

Live performances, sports events, rituals, religious ceremonies, storytelling, oral history

Archival records, maps, geographic data, cultural/physical artifacts, material culture

Primary research studies, study characteristics, reported results, quality assessment scores

Parameters, mathematical methods/techniques, existing theories/models, empirical data for validation/training/calibration

Examples: Generated Data

Critical appraisal, syntheses of findings, bibliographic data, summary tables, thematic maps, narrative syntheses

Media content analyses, thematic analyses, coded datasets, social media analytics, data extraction sheets, quality assessment

Annotated texts/images, transcriptions, thematic/textual analyses, character analyses

Annotations, notes, syntheses of findings, thematic/narrative/comparative analyses, visual/auditory analyses

Thematic/curated collections, annotated images, symbols/motifs extracted, databases, 3D models, critical analyses

Moderator's notes, audio/video recordings, flipchart notes, (annotated) transcripts, thematic analyses, coding frameworks

Catalogue entries, inventories, metadata, contextual/comparative analyses

Critical reviews, performance analyses, noted impressions, reflective notes, photographs, coding frameworks

Field notes, diaries, thematic analyses, coded transcripts, images, ethnographic reports

Data extraction sheets, publication bias assessments, sensitivity analyses, critical appraisal

Mathematical equations, conceptual frameworks, analytical results, performance metrics, visualisations, sensitivity/error analyses, formulas, code, software

Note that the abovementioned examples of data are non-exhaustive.

Top 4 Critical RDM Strategies to Consider

1. Safekeeping of digital / physical data
2. File Naming & Folder Structure
3. Correct data storage (check with your institution)
4. Documentation and Metadata

Simple Tools to Support Your RDM

- **Data Management Plan (DMP)** for your overall strategy as to research data lifecycle
- **Word processors and spreadsheets** for data and process documentation
- **Electronic Lab Notebooks** to keep track of and document your research
- **Bibliographic/Reference Management Tools** to keep up with literature, documents, and other references

Do you want to know more about RDM?

Check out VUB's RDM resources on Zenodo:

Ünver, Ö. (2025). "No Data" to Manage? Think Again!. Flemish Research Data Network Day (FRDN Day), Brussels. Vrije Universiteit Brussel.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15495601>

What is qualitative data?

Qualitative data refers to information that is not gathered in numerical form but rather describes qualities or characteristics.

- Natural language
 - Textual
 - Visual
-
- **Heterogeneous, can take many forms & wide variety of collection methods**
Photography, audio recordings, video, interviews, diary accounts, unstructured observations,...

Reasoning for making data reusable

- Increasing transparency in research process
- Re-analysis for new research questions
- Enhance visibility of existing research

For qualitative research in particular:

- **Often time & resource intensive** → already available data could be reused
- **Reduce the burden of participants in qualitative studies**
- **Rich data** → often allows for a multitude of research questions to be answered

Unique challenges

- **Personal & sensitive information**

- Legal constraints (e.g. GDPR, copyright)
- Sensitive nature of data (e.g. business information)
- Potential risks for individuals
- De-identification of data can often lead to information loss

- **Context sensitive:**

- Hard to capture all the contextual information that is essential for interpretation
- Variety and richness of data
- Interaction between researcher and study participant/objects

- **Subjectivity**

- Researcher's positionality

OS focus?

GUIDEBOOK

Making Qualitative Data Reusable

Making Qualitative Data Reusable – Guidebook DANS

- Verburg, M., Braukmann, R., & Mahabier, W. (2023). Making Qualitative Data Reusable - A Short Guidebook For Researchers And Data Stewards Working With Qualitative Data (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8160880>
- Revised version will be published soon
- Source material for this presentation

CESSDA

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

- Provides large-scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the social sciences community, incl.
 - A data discovery portal
 - Data management training
 - Controlled vocabulary services
- National service provider for Belgium: [SODHA](https://www.sodha.be/)

<https://www.cessda.eu/>

Project Planning & Informed Consent

Planning

Data Management Plan (DMP)

DATA SUMMARY

DOCUMENTATION
& METADATA

DATA STORAGE &
BACKUP

DATA
PRESERVATION

DATA SHARING
& REUSE

RESPONSIBILITIES
& RESOURCES

Research data overview table – Example

Dataset name	Description	New or reused	Digital or physical	Digital data type	Digital data Format	Volume
Questionnaire	List of questions and answer options of the survey	Reused	Digital	Other	pdf	< 1 MB
Survey results	Responses to the online survey, collected without direct identifiers	New	Digital	Observational	csv, sav	< 10 MB
Recorded interviews	Video recordings of interviews	new	Digital	Observational	mp4	< 1 TB
Interview transcriptions	Pseudonymised transcriptions of recorded interviews	new		Observational	docx, pdf	< 20 MB
Anonymised transcriptions	Anonymised version of transcripts	New		Observational	docx, pdf	< 20 MB
Notes	Notes taken during data collection	New	Digital	Observational	docx	<10 MB
Analysis code	Statistical code in R used to analyse survey results	new		Software	R	< 1 MB
Visualisations	Visualisations of survey results	New	Digital	Observational	SVG, PNG	< 1 GB
Code file	Linking interview participants to pseudonyms	New	Digital	Other	csv	< 1 MB

Planning your project

Tools

- [CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide](#)
 - [Checklist](#) questions to consider
- [Qualitative Data Repository DMP checklist](#)

Data Management Expert Guide (DMEG)

The DMEG is designed by European experts to help social science researchers make their research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (**FAIR**).

You will be guided by different European experts who are - on a daily basis - busy ensuring long-term access to valuable social science datasets, available for discovery and reuse at one of the [CESSDA social science data archives](#).

You can [download](#) the full DMEG for your personal study offline (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3820473](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3820473)). PDFs for every [single chapter](#) are also available for being printed as handouts for training.

See also the pilot [interactive game version](#) of the guide!

To take into consideration

Personal data

- Can I de-identify the personal data? How would this affect the usefulness of the data?
- Do I have permission/consent to share personal data without de-identification?
- Can I include reusability of data in my informed consent forms?
- Can I keep the personal information separate from information that can be shared openly?

Sensitive data

- Are my participants at risk if information from the study would become available?
- Can I keep the sensitive information separate from information that could be shared openly?
- Does this level of sensitivity in my data prohibit all types of data sharing, or could I consider sharing under specific circumstances (e.g. restricted access, a secure environment)?
- What additional measures will have to be undertaken to manage the sensitive data in line with institutional policies?

To take into consideration

Collaborators

- Which other parties are involved?
- How do they feel about making the data reusable & will they be supportive?
- Who owns the data?
- How can I guarantee a permanent point of contact, in particular if I restrict access?

Participants

- Is it in the interest of my participants to make the data available?
- Are there particular benefits or risks for them?
- How can I support the autonomy of my participants regarding their data?

To take into consideration

(Open) formats & tools

- In what formats will I collect my data?
- Can I use open formats so that it can be read into different analysis programs?
- What tools will I be using to process my data?

Documenting the research process

- With the methods I am planning to use, how can I ensure that I document the research process as best as possible to make it understandable for others?

Preparing informed consent

- **Seek consent for archiving and sharing of data**
- **Think about sharing and reuse upfront**
 - Know what you want to be open & what to be restricted/closed
 - Will it be hard to de-identify data? → ask for consent for sharing identifiable personal data
 - E.g. Video data, data from well-known organisations or individuals
 - Consider your participants in making decisions on what kind of data you want to share
- **Include information in informed consent form**

Lots of templates available

[University of Oxford](#), [CESSDA DMEG](#), [Utrecht University](#), [TU Delft](#), [QESB](#)

Data Processing & Tools

Collecting & Processing data

Software & tools

- For recording, transcription & speech recognition, annotation, de-identification...
- **Free & open source alternatives?**
- **Adhering to community standards**

- **Know your tools!**
- **Consider privacy & security aspects of tools**
 - Not all will be appropriate to use
 - Evaluate use for individual study, remain sceptical
 - Run tool locally & control where data is stored and kept

Organising and documenting qualitative data

- **Consider future reusability of your data**
- **Provide enough contextual documentation**
 - Difficult to specify
 - Often not enough
 - But essential for transparency in qualitative research
- **Guidance on good practices regarding file names and folder structure + examples of documenting qualitative data**

Transparency in data collection & analysis

Coding

- Content analysis, thematic analysis, & other coding methods
- Clear & detailed explanation how codes were created, applied, adjusted
- Coding process well-documented and transparent, including decisions made and rationale
 - **Codebook:** define & describe each code
 - Explain how codes are created & applied (deductive/inductive)
 - Record changes over time
 - Justify coding decisions
 - Multiple coders: describe how consensus is reached, how coders are trained, how consistency is overseen

Transparency in data collection & analysis

Analytical decision-making

- Document reasoning behind interpretive choices and analytical paths
 - Framework: state theory/method used
 - Provide detailed account of your data analysis
 - Describe quality checks
 - Explain how you used triangulation to validate findings + rationale
 - Document key analytical decision
 - Reflect

Transparency in data collection & analysis

Use of software

- Document the use of software and decisions linked to it
 - State which versions and settings were used
 - Describe purpose: how and why was the software employed?
 - Document any analyses performed outside the software (e.g. integration of manual analysis)
 - Consider containerisation: “freezing” the version used

De-identification of personal data

- **Important to protect privacy**
- **Increase possibilities of data sharing & reuse**
- **Anonymising or pseudonymising**
- **Safe storage or processing environment**

- **However, de-identification often not possible or desirable**
 - Too much information loss
 - Need to find balance between privacy and understandability

A VISUAL GUIDE TO PRACTICAL DATA DE-IDENTIFICATION

What do scientists, regulators and lawyers mean when they talk about de-identification? How does anonymous data differ from pseudonymous or de-identified information? Data identifiability is not binary. Data lies on a spectrum with multiple shades of identifiability.

DEGREES OF IDENTIFIABILITY

Information containing direct and indirect identifiers.

PSEUDONYMOUS DATA

Information from which direct identifiers have been eliminated or transformed, but indirect identifiers remain intact.

DE-IDENTIFIED DATA

Direct and known indirect identifiers have been removed or manipulated to break the linkage to real world identities.

ANONYMOUS DATA

Direct and indirect identifiers have been removed or manipulated together with mathematical and technical guarantees to prevent re-identification.

This is a primer on how to distinguish different categories of data.

DIRECT IDENTIFIERS
 Data that identifies a person without additional information or by linking to information in the public domain (e.g., name, SSN)

INDIRECT IDENTIFIERS
 Data that identifies an individual indirectly. Helps connect pieces of information until an individual can be singled out (e.g., DOB, gender)

SAFEGUARDS and CONTROLS
 Technical, organizational and legal controls preventing employees, researchers or other third parties from re-identifying individuals

	EXPLICITLY PERSONAL	POTENTIALLY IDENTIFIABLE	NOT READILY IDENTIFIABLE	KEY CODED	PSEUDONYMOUS	PROTECTED PSEUDONYMOUS	DE-IDENTIFIED	PROTECTED DE-IDENTIFIED	ANONYMOUS	AGGREGATED ANONYMOUS
DIRECT IDENTIFIERS	INTACT	PARTIALLY MASKED	PARTIALLY MASKED	ELIMINATED or TRANSFORMED	ELIMINATED or TRANSFORMED					
INDIRECT IDENTIFIERS	INTACT	INTACT	INTACT	INTACT	INTACT	INTACT	ELIMINATED or TRANSFORMED	ELIMINATED or TRANSFORMED	ELIMINATED or TRANSFORMED	ELIMINATED or TRANSFORMED
SAFEGUARDS and CONTROLS	NOT RELEVANT due to nature of data	LIMITED or NONE IN PLACE	CONTROLS IN PLACE	CONTROLS IN PLACE	LIMITED or NONE IN PLACE	CONTROLS IN PLACE	LIMITED or NONE IN PLACE	CONTROLS IN PLACE	NOT RELEVANT due to nature of data	NOT RELEVANT due to high degree of data aggregation

SELECTED EXAMPLES

Name, address, phone number, SSN, government-issued ID (e.g., Jane Smith, 123 Main Street, 555-555-5555)

Unique device ID, license plate, medical record number, cookie, IP address (e.g., MAC address 68:A8:6D:35:65:03)

Same as Potentially Identifiable except data are also protected by safeguards and controls (e.g., hashed MAC addresses & legal representations)

Clinical or research datasets where only curator retains key (e.g., Jane Smith, diabetes, HgB 15.1 g/dl = Csrk123)

Unique, artificial pseudonyms replace direct identifiers (e.g., HIPAA Limited Datasets, John Doe = 5L7T LX619Z) (unique sequence not used anywhere else)

Same as Pseudonymous, except data are also protected by safeguards and controls

Data are suppressed, generalized, perturbed, swapped, etc. (e.g., GPA: 3.2 = 3.0-3.5, gender: female = gender: male)

Same as De-Identified, except data are also protected by safeguards and controls

For example, noise is calibrated to a data set to hide whether an individual is present or not (differential privacy)

Very highly aggregated data (e.g., statistical data, census data, or population data that 52.6% of Washington, DC residents are women)

De-identification techniques

- Suppression
- Generalisation
- Replacement
- Top- and bottom coding
- Adding noise
- Permutation

Guidance

- Campbell R, Javorka M, Engleton J, Fishwick K, Gregory K, Goodman-Williams R. Open-Science Guidance for Qualitative Research: An Empirically Validated Approach for De-Identifying Sensitive Narrative Data. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*. 2023;6(4). doi:[10.1177/25152459231205832](https://doi.org/10.1177/25152459231205832)
 - “a methodological framework for remediating sensitive narrative data”
- **[Methods for anonymising qualitative data | Erasmus University Rotterdam](#)**
- **[Anonymising qualitative data - UK Data Service](#)**
- **[De-Identification - Qualitative Data Repository](#)**
- **[Data Privacy Handbook - Utrecht University](#)**
- **[Anonymisation and Personal Data - Finnish Social Science Data Archive \(FSD\)](#)**

Some tools for de-identifying qualitative data

- **anonymoUUS**
 - [GitHub - UtrechtUniversity/anonymouus: Python package to replace identifiable strings in multiple files and folders at once.](#)
- **UKDS text anonymisation helper tool**
- **Textwash Free Automated Multi-language Text Anonymisation for Open Science**

- **Atlas.ti**
- **Nvivo**

Data Publishing & Access Control

Archiving and sharing

Trustworthy repositories

■ Domain-specific

- [SODHA](#)
- [DANS Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities](#)

■ Institutional data repository

- [KU Leuven RDR](#)
- [DataverseNL](#)
- Future FAIRVault
 - UAntwerpen
 - UGent
 - VUB
 - UHasselt

<https://re3data.org>
<https://fairsharing.org/>

ERICs – European Research Infrastructure Consortia

- CLARIN for digital language data:
<https://www.clarin.eu/content/depositing-services>
- DARIAH for (digital) arts and humanities :
<https://www.dariah.eu/tools-services/tools-and-services/>
- CESSDA for social sciences: <https://www.cessda.eu/>
- And [more](#)

Welcome to SODHA, the **Belgian federal data archive for social sciences** and the **digital humanities!**

Here you can **find** and **deposit** social science and digital humanities data in reusable form. Published datasets receive a DOI, making them citable like other types of publications. SODHA promotes **open data** by enabling **reuse** of research data and by **safely preserving** datasets in the long term.

SODHA is the Belgian service provider in the [Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives \(CESSDA\)](#) and is hosted by the [State Archives of Belgium](#). SODHA was built with the help of [DEMO \(UCLouvain\)](#) and [Interface Demography \(VUB\)](#).

You can consult the [SODHA Guide here](#), and you can read our [policies here](#).

Want to learn more about SODHA? Consult [our brochure](#) or [our presentation on the State Archives' website](#).

If you have any question, you can contact us at sodha@arch.be.

[Collapse Description \[-\]](#)

State Archives of Belgium

BASS

Belgian Archives for Social Sciences

KBR

Royal Library of Belgium

The Social Study

Search this dataverse...

[Advanced Search](#)

[+ Add Data](#)

[Dataverses \(5\)](#)

[Datasets \(159\)](#)

[Files \(2,611\)](#)

Dataverse Category

[Organization or Institution \(3\)](#)

[Department \(1\)](#)

[Research Project \(1\)](#)

Publication Year

[2022-2023 \(4\)](#)

1 to 10 of 164 Results

[Sort ▾](#)

The FLANDMOT database: L2 Motivation in French and English among 1,300 Flemish Secondary-School Learners

Aug 27, 2025

Thewissen, Jennifer, Anishchanka, Alena, 2025, "The FLANDMOT database: L2 Motivation in French and English among 1,300 Flemish Secondary-School Learners", <https://doi.org/10.34834/DVN/I23Q5HC>, Social Sciences and Digital Humanities Archive – SODHA, V1

This database was collected in 2022-2023 in secondary schools across Flanders to gain access into learners' motivational profiles for L2 English and L2 French. The questionnaire items were partly created based on Zoltán Dörnyei's theoretical framework of motivation (integrative...

Home » [Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities](#)

Data Station Social Sciences and Humanities

This data station allows you to deposit and search for data within the social sciences and humanities. The metadata of our Data Station SSH is also available in the national ODISSEI portal and the European CESSDA Data Catalogue.

If you have a question, please check the [frequently asked questions](#) or send your question to Data Station Managers Ricarda Braukmann (Social Sciences) and Jetze Touber (Humanities).

Deposit data

Deposit >>>

[Need help with depositing?](#)

Search data

Zoekopdracht

Search

[Need help with your search?](#)

Preferred file formats

Balance between open formats and proprietary community standards

Open

- + long-term sustainability (migration)
- + accessible to all without software installation
- If converted from proprietary format, information could be lost

Proprietary community standard

- + generally used and understood in the community
- + no risk of information loss due to conversion
- Risk of poor long-term sustainability (no migration, software updates, obsolescence)
- Not/less accessible to other potential future users

DANS

Preferred file formats

TYPE	PREFERRED FORMATS	NON-PREFERRED FORMATS
Text documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PDF/A (.pdf) • ODT (.odt) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microsoft Word (.doc) • Office Open XML (.docx) • Rich Text File (.rtf) • PDF other than PDF/A (.pdf)
Plain text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unicode text (.txt) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-Unicode text (.txt)
Markup language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • XML (.xml) • HTML (.html) • Related files: .css, .xslt, .js, .es • Markdown (.md) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SGML (.sgml)
Programming languages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MATLAB • NETCDF • Text-Fabric • Python 	
Spreadsheets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ODS (.ods) • CSV (.csv) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Microsoft Excel (.xls) • Office Open XML Workbook (.xlsx) • PDF/A (.pdf)
Raster images	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JPEG (.jpg, .jpeg) • TIFF (.tif, .tiff) • PNG (.png) • JPEG 2000 (.jp2) • DICOM (.dcm) 	
Vector images	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SVG (.svg) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adobe Illustrator (.ai) • EPS (.eps) • WMF/EMF (.wmf, .emf) • CDR (.cdr)
Audio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BMF (.bmf) • MXF (.mxf) • Matroska (.mka) • FLAC (.flac) • OPUS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WAVE (.wav) • MP3 (.mp3) • AAC (.aac, .m4a) • AIFF (.aif, .aiff) • OGG (.ogg)
Video	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MXF (.mxf) • Matroska (.mkv) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPEG-4 (.mp4, .m4a, ...) • MPEG-2 (.mpg, .mpeg, .m2v, ...) • AVI (.avi) • QuickTime (.mov, .qt)

Documentation & metadata

- **Metadata for findability**
- **Metadata standards**
 - For social sciences: Data Documentation Initiative codebook, [DDI 2.5](#)
 - CESSDA Metadata Model
- **Detailing context of research**
- **Notes, logs, methodological decisions, ...**
 - Essential for fostering understanding and potential reuse
- When data sharing is not possible/feasible, **include supplementary materials or detailed documentation** regarding the data and research

Reflective Reporting of Findings

▪ Contextualization

- Background → context, setting, participants, influencing factors
- Rich description
- Data excerpts: show links between data and findings
- Discuss limitations of your approach and possible impact

Reflective Reporting of Findings

▪ Reflexivity

- Critically reflect on own perspectives, values, assumptions and experiences
- Acknowledge subjectivity, manage bias, provide readers with context
- Allows readers to assess researcher's positionality
 - Self-awareness
 - Reflect on power dynamics
 - Question choices in design, methods and interpretation
 - Transparency

As open as possible, as closed as necessary

Following Open Science principles, you want to publish Open Access where possible

- Often not possible/desirable for qualitative research

Consider

- Sensitivity → mitigating risks
- Copyright & other legal obligations → understand & comply
- Personal data (AVG/GDPR) → protection

Qualitative data reuse decision tree

as open as possible, as closed as necessary

Verburg, M., Braukmann, R., & Mahabier, W. (2023). Decision Tree - Making Qualitative Data Reusable (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8160890>

Qualitative data reuse decision tree

as open as possible, as closed as necessary

Archive open access

Your data is not sensitive, and if your dataset contains personal data you have informed consent that allows the open sharing of data, or the personal data can be anonymised adequately.

Consider to archive your data open access in trustworthy digital repository like the DANS Data Station SSH. CC0 license is recommended. Include metadata and documentation to improve the reusability.

Archive restricted access

Your data contains personal information that you are not allowed to share open access, but your informed consent allows data sharing with specific conditions.

Consider to archive your data in trustworthy digital repository that allows restricted access, like the DANS Data Station SSH. Include metadata and documentation to improve the reusability. Establish a Data Access Protocol to accept or reject requests.

Secure environment

Your data is sensitive and/or contains personal data and you don't have informed consent to share it. Consider using secure environments where the data remains under your control.

Publish project documentation and metadata about your data to make it findable.

Decentralised reanalysis

Your data is sensitive and/or contains personal data and you don't have informed consent to share it. Consider offering your data for decentralised reanalysis, where you reanalyse your data based on analysis protocols from other researchers.

Publish project documentation and metadata about your data to make it findable.

Publish metadata only

Your data is sensitive and/or contains personal data and you don't have informed consent to share it. Secure environments or decentralised reanalysis are not possible for you.

Publish project documentation and metadata about your project to make it findable.

Verburg, M., Braukmann, R., & Mahabier, W. (2023). Decision Tree - Making Qualitative Data Reusable (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8160890>

Restricted access

- **Access under certain conditions**
- **Follow a data access protocol**
 - Questions to consider when restricting access
 - Do you allow
 - Use beyond research?
 - Commercial use?
 - Educational use?
 - Use outside institution, outside Europe?
 - Do you require a motivation for reuse? How is it evaluated?
 - Who is responsible to evaluate requests? How is this organized?
 - Easier to manage access
 - Easier for potential users to assess eligibility

DAP template:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14646180>

Access levels

Personal data

Confidential
data

Sensitive data

Third-party
data

Copyright

Valorization

Open Access (with open license!)

- Available for everyone and for every use
- Released under open, standard licenses (CC0, CC-BY)

Restricted access

- Available to others, but not openly available
- Limits on who can access and for what purpose
 - Non-disclosure agreements
 - Personal data, but available for research purposes
 - ...
- Explain access conditions and the requirements that must be met clearly

Closed access

- No access possible, not shared under any circumstances
 - Under embargo
 - Unable to share

Publish metadata only

- **None of the options are applicable to your situation**
- **Consider publishing documentation, materials and as much metadata as possible**
 - Discoverability of research project
 - Documentation and materials might be useful for reuse regardless of the data
- **Not all repositories accept metadata-only records**
- **But alternatives:**
 - OSF
 - Zenodo

FAIR qualitative data

- **Findable**

- ✓ Ensure discoverability of data and materials
- ✓ Metadata

- **Accessible**

- ✓ FAIR data \neq open data
- ✓ Access conditions are clear

- **Interoperable**

- ✓ Standards, controlled vocabularies

- **Reusable**

- ✓ Documentation
- ✓ Licensing

Conclusions

- **Expand our views of what ‘sharing data’ means**
- **Plan for openness from the start of your project**
- **Balance openness with protection**
- **Context matter**

Conclusions

- **Carefully evaluate projects and processes to maximize the reusability of your data & other materials/outputs**
 - Some data cannot be made available to other researchers at all
 - Some can be made available after de-identification
 - Some can be made available with restrictions
 - Documentation and information about the study can likely be made available in all cases
 - ✓ Provide information about existing data even if they cannot access the data itself
 - ✓ Transparency in data collection & analysis

Questions?

Contact:

linde.tuybens@uantwerpen.be
or rdm-support@uantwerpen.be

or visit our webpages:

[Research Data Management | University of Antwerp \(uantwerpen.be\)](https://rdm.uantwerpen.be)

